

**PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF VASCULAR INSUFFICIENCY.
HYPERTENSION STATUS AND THEIR TYPES, CHARACTERISTICS
IN CHILDREN**

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Abstract. In this article, the pathophysiology of vascular insufficiency. The state of hypertension and its types, characteristics in children are described in detail and relevant facts are cited.

Key words: vascular insufficiency, pathophysiology, hypertensive state, symptoms, etc.

Currently, diseases of the cardiovascular system are the most widespread in the world and have taken the form of an epidemic without exaggeration. According to the experts of the World Health Organization, one death occurs every 32 seconds due to diseases of the cardiovascular system. Ischemic heart disease (which primarily includes heart attack, angina pectoris, and myocardial infarction) is the most deadly among diseases of the cardiovascular system. If we consider 100% of deaths due to diseases of the cardiovascular system, 52.5% of them occur as a result of heart attack, angina pectoris, and infarction. Death is observed more and more in older people. Heart attacks occur "unexpectedly" and in most cases can lead to sudden death. More than half of the deaths due to myocardial infarction occur in the first hours of the attack, when patients do not even have time to seek medical help. Other fatal diseases of the cardiovascular system include: rheumatic heart attacks, angina pectoris, hypertension, congenital and acquired heart defects, etc. enters. Diseases of the cardiovascular system - diseases of the heart, arteries and veins. They are many and varied. Some of these diseases (rheumatism, myocarditis, etc.) damage the heart, some damage arteries (atherosclerosis) or veins (for example, thrombophlebitis), others damage the

entire cardiovascular system (hypertension). Ischemic heart disease is caused by insufficient blood supply to the heart muscles. Basically, it is caused by atherosclerotic changes of the coronary arteries, spasm, as well as blood clots (thrombosis) in their cavity, etc.

Since the time of pressure decrease in diastole is longer than the time of rise in systole, the average pressure value is closer to the diastolic pressure. An increase in arterial pressure is called arterial hypertension, and a decrease in arterial pressure is called arterial hypotension. There are two methods of determination of arterial pressure: blood or direct and non-blood-indirect methods. In 1733, S. Hales determined arterial pressure in horses using the blood method. Later, the German scientist K. Ludwig improved this method and recorded a characteristic curve by connecting it to recording devices. In animals, a glass cannula or catheter is inserted into the arteries, and its end is connected to a manometer with a rigid glass container, the catheter and the glass container are filled with an anticoagulant solution to prevent blood from clotting, and the arterial blood pressure curve is recorded. Arterial hypertension is the most common cardiovascular disease. is the most common and is more common among older people. It is the main pathogenetic factor that often causes death or disability, such as myocardial infarction, stroke, heart failure. Chronic venous insufficiency pathophysiology is either due to reflux (backward flow) or obstruction of venous blood flow. Chronic venous insufficiency can develop from the protracted valvular incompetence of superficial veins, deep veins or perforating veins that connect them. In all cases, the result is venous hypertension of the lower extremities.

Superficial incompetence is usually due to weakened or abnormally shaped valves or widened venous diameter which prevents normal valve congruence. The leaky valve in most cases is located near the termination of the greater saphenous vein into the common femoral vein. While in some cases the valve dysfunction

may be congenital, it can also be a result of trauma, prolonged standing, hormonal changes or thrombosis. Deep vein dysfunction is usually owing to the previous DVT which results in inflammation, valve scarring and adhesion, and luminal narrowing. Perforating vein valvular failure allows higher pressure to enter the superficial venous system. The subsequent dilation prevents the proper closure of the valve cusps in the superficial veins. Most patients will also have the disease in the superficial veins. The resting venous pressure is a summation of the outflow obstruction, capillary inflow, valve function, and muscle pump function. Regardless of the cause, the persistently elevated venous hydrostatic pressure may result in lower extremity pain, edema, and venous microangiopathy. Some patients develop permanent skin hyperpigmentation from hemosiderin deposition as red blood cells extravasate into the surrounding tissue. Many of these patients will also have lipodermatosclerosis, which is skin thickening from fibrosis of subcutaneous fat. As the disease progresses, the perturbed microcirculation and dermal weakening can result in ulcer formation.

Arterial hypotension (hypotonic disease) is relatively rare. It is observed in many diseases of the cardiovascular system (myocardial infarction, cardiomyopathy, myocarditis), neuroses, hypothyroidism, stroke, in the form of arterial hypotonia syndrome. In clinical practice, heart muscle inflammation - myocarditis and non-inflammatory damage - myocardiodystrophy are observed more often. Endocarditis (inflammation of the lining of the heart) is caused by rheumatism and other acquired heart defects. Leerycarditis is rare. As a result of ischemic heart disease, myocarditis and myocardiodystrophy, as well as neurotic conditions, cardiac arrhythmias and heart block can occur. Cardiac arrhythmias are acceleration (tachycardia) or slowing (bradycardia) of heart contractions (beating), abnormal additional heart contractions (extrasystole); sudden acceleration of heart rate (paroxysmal tachycardia); it is manifested in incorrect contraction of the heart at different time intervals (oscillating arrhythmia) and

others. Heart block is a disruption of nerve impulse transmission in the conduction system of the heart (for example, interruption of impulse transmission from the chambers to the ventricles or to the bundles of the bundle of His). When the activity of the nervous system of the heart is disturbed due to neuroses, along with arrhythmias, there are also sensations of throbbing, stabbing, throbbing pain in the heart. Atherosclerosis and hypertension are common diseases of arterial vessels, and most of them go together. Atherosclerosis damages not only the coronary vessels, but also the aorta and its large branches, including the renal artery, cerebral vessels (stroke), and the peripheral vessels of the arm. Inflammation of arterial vessels — arteritis is more often caused by infectious (eg, wound, sepsis) and allergic (see Serum sickness) and collagen diseases. The clinical form is obliterating endarteritis, aortic panarteritis, etc. Varicose veins and thrombophlebitis are common diseases of the veins. Heart failure is manifested by pathological signs (bruising of the skin, shortness of breath, swelling of the legs, etc.) indicating that the heart cannot perform the full functional load imposed on it; shortness of breath while doing something is a pathological symptom.

Patients with chronic venous insufficiency commonly present initially with a combination of dependent pitting edema, leg discomfort, and fatigue, and itching. Although there can be variations in presentation among patients, certain features are more prevalent: pain, cramping, itching, prickling, and throbbing sensation. Patients may describe symptoms that improve with rest and leg elevation, and with no association for exercise. This latter feature can be used to distinguish venous from arterial claudication. As their disease progresses, the presence of varicose veins and tenderness can be noted along with refractory edema and skin changes. Patients with advanced disease will present with a severe blanched skin lesion, dermal atrophy, hyperpigmentation, dilated venous capillaries, and ulcer formation most commonly overlying the medial malleolus.

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